

Customer Perception on Green Banking Initiatives: A Study Conducted among Professionals in Kerala

Dr. Issac George

*Associate Professor & HoD; MBA Department, St Philomena's College (Autonomous)
Mysuru; Karnataka; India*

Dr. Sadia Tabassum

Associate Professor, MBA, St Philomena's College (Autonomous) Mysuru; Karnataka; India

Abstract: The escalating concern for environmental sustainability has prompted organizations, including those in the banking sector, to adopt eco-friendly practices. Green banking, which focuses on reducing paper usage and carbon footprints through technology-enabled transactions, has gained significant attention. This study explores the necessity of green banking practices and examines customer perception of these initiatives in the banking sector. A survey was conducted among 50 doctors working in Thrissur district, Kerala. Primary data was collected and analyzed using statistical tools. In the post-COVID-19 pandemic era, this study is particularly relevant as banking authorities and customers increasingly prefer contactless transactions. This research work focuses on Necessity of green banking practices and customer perception of green banking initiatives. Thereby identifying the Impact of technology on reducing paper usage and carbon footprints. This study aims to provide valuable insights into the adoption and effectiveness of green banking practices, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable and environmentally conscious banking sector.

Keywords: Green Banking, Environmental Issues, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking

Introduction:

The banking sector plays a pivotal role in the economic development of nations, regardless of their level of advancement—developed, developing, or underdeveloped. In India, banks serve as the backbone of the financial system and are essential for the country's economic growth. Technological advancements and a rise in per capita income have increased reliance on banks, leading to a significant growth in account holders and transaction volumes. Even marginalized communities depend on banks for accessing government subsidies and grants, further driving this growth. The demand for corporate and retail loans has also surged, particularly in sectors such as real estate, services, consumer goods, and agriculture, contributing to credit expansion. Concurrently, advancements in technology have transformed banking operations, encouraging paperless, technology-driven transactions. Digital banking now enables customers to carry out transactions 24/7, in alignment with the Reserve Bank of India's (RBI) "Payment System Vision 2021," which forecasted an increase in digital transactions to 8,707 crores by December 2021.

Although the banking sector is not a direct contributor to pollution, its activities—such as energy usage and paper consumption—have indirect environmental implications. Recognizing this, banks are adopting eco-friendly measures, such as digitalization, to reduce carbon footprints. Multinational banks have led the charge by integrating sustainable practices into their operations, shifting the traditional focus from "profit only" to a more holistic model of "people, planet, and profit." The Indian banking sector, under the guidance of the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), is actively promoting environmentally and socially responsible practices. This shift reflects a growing societal concern for environmental protection, prompting businesses to adopt greener operational models. Banks are now encouraging clients to invest in eco-friendly ventures and prioritize lending to companies that embrace sustainable practices. This approach, known as "green banking," involves:

- **Integrating environmental considerations into banking operations:** This includes streamlining processes, leveraging technology, and encouraging customers to adopt eco-friendly banking habits.
- **Promoting digital transactions:** Digital banking services like online account opening, mobile banking, and digital fund transfers minimize paper consumption and reduce the environmental impact of banking activities.
- **Adopting sustainable payment systems:** Implementing centralized payment systems and electronic benefit transfers further enhances efficiency and reduces the environmental footprint.

Many studies across the globe have shown a significant reduction in operational cost because of green banking practices. *Rashid, 2020*, in his study have pointed that the green banking initiatives have reduced the cost of banks and reduced the risks of contaminations. *Khairunnessa et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2021*, in their study green banking aimed protecting the environment, society and economy at a large scale. By embracing these initiatives, the banking sector plays a crucial role in supporting environmental sustainability and contributing to a greener future.

This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of green banking practices in driving the adoption of mobile and internet banking among customers. Specifically, it seeks to understand customer perceptions regarding green banking initiatives implemented by nationalized banks in India. The research focuses on the views of doctors residing in Thrissur district. Given the evolving customer behaviour towards online banking, this study has significant implications for the future of banking services. Implications to ensure business continuity. Similarly, online training and development systems for continuous capacity growth initiatives is required to minimize the costs of banks and reduce the risks of contamination (Rashid, 2020). He said that customers do not need banks as they need banking. As such, it is high time financial institutions introduce green banking systems including online banking, online payments, and technological innovations to meet customer's need and also minimize the effect of crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Green banking (GB) is a type of bank operation aimed at protecting the

environment (natural resources), society and economy Adaptation of technology to the banking systems is essential to the management of COVID-19 complications to ensure business continuity. Similarly, online training and development systems for continuous capacity growth initiatives is required to minimize the costs of banks and reduce the risks of contamination(Rashid, 2020). He said that customers do not need banks as they need banking. As such, it is high time financial institutions introduce green banking systems including online banking, online payments, and technological innovations to meet customer's need and also minimize the effect of crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Green banking (GB) is a type of bank operation aimed at protecting the environment (natural resources), society and economy Adaptation of technology to the banking systems is essential to the management of COVID-19

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Indian Banking System

A bank is a financial institution that accepts deposits and extends loans to households, businesses, and the government. The Indian banking sector, consisting of 12 public sector banks, 22 private sector banks, 44 foreign banks, 43 regional rural banks, 1,484 urban cooperative banks and 96,000 rural cooperative banks in addition to cooperative credit institutions and numerous regional and cooperative banks, all of these are crucial to the nation's economy. As of March 2021, India had 213,575 ATMs. Banks play an intermediary role, connecting surplus funds with capital deficits, and are vital to economic development by promoting production, distribution, and consumption.

The banking sector in India, despite facing challenges, has played a key role in supporting agricultural development and overall economic growth. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has emphasized sustainability and responsible banking practices. The sector's growth has been more qualitative than quantitative, with rising disposable incomes and easier access to credit contributing to its expansion.

India's banking sector is increasingly adopting international banking standards, including the establishment of a public credit registry (PCR). Efforts to expand banking services in rural areas and increase financial inclusion through initiatives like Pradhan Mantri Jan Dhan Yojana are underway. Additionally, banks are embracing technology for faster, more secure services and expanding into non-banking areas like insurance and mutual funds.

According to the report published by *Greenwich Associates* 2016, the banks are adopting technology to deliver faster, more transparent services to their clients. They are given special attention to the security of their customers and have entered services like insurance, mutual funds, share trading etc which are not come under this sector. Rising income is expected to enhance the need for banking services in rural areas, and therefore, drive the growth of the sector. The digital payments revolution will trigger massive changes in the way credit is disbursed in India. Debit cards have radically replaced credit cards as the preferred payment mode in India after demonetization. In May 2021, *Unified Payments Interface (UPI)* recorded 2.54 billion transactions worth Rs. 4.91 lakh crore (US\$ 67.32 billion). *Thombre 2011*, pointed out that the banks should step backward towards providing funds to those projects that are having negative impact on environment balance. Its moral responsibility of the banks to encourage those projects that support environmental and social wellbeing. The digital payments revolution, driven by UPI and other digital platforms, has significantly transformed the banking landscape, with debit cards replacing credit cards as the preferred payment method post-demonetization.

Green Banking Initiatives:

Globalization, urbanization, and technological advancements have led to the depletion of greenery, resulting in severe environmental threats. Overuse of natural resources has caused pollution, which affects the quality of products and services. In response, organizations are increasingly adopting environmentally friendly, resource-efficient, and low-carbon practices. India, one of the most polluted countries, has mandated industries to reduce pollution and adopt eco-friendly measures.

Initially, banks evaluated their performance based on profits, but this focus has shifted. Green banking, introduced in the U.S. in 2009 and later by SBI in India, promotes environmentally sustainable practices. Examples include using online banking instead of branch visits and supporting local green initiatives. While green banking initially reached only educated and entrepreneurial individuals, increased internet usage has boosted its adoption.

Green banking, also known as ethical or sustainable banking, focuses on funding projects that adhere to environmental safety standards. It includes green loans, green savings accounts, and online/mobile banking. Bangladesh has been a leader in green banking, implementing policies to encourage eco-friendly projects and reduce carbon footprints. While green banking is gaining traction globally, especially in Bangladesh, it remains underdeveloped in India. Studies suggest that Indian banks need to adopt green banking strategies to compete globally. Despite challenges like high costs, green banking offers convenience for customers, such as reducing bank visits through online and mobile banking.

In a study conducted by *Masukujjaman & Aktar (2014)* have found out that very less private as well as public banks are doing in in-house environment management in volume and scale and contributing significantly to the sustainable financing and most of the banking sector are in the

initial stage in identifying and committed the green banking and these banks are far behind their counterparts from developed countries. *Vijay & Sangepu (2013)*, have pointed the ideal of green savings money and its advantages. There has been a lot of study and steps were taken for the green banking in the neighboring countries, but many economists have pointed out that green banking initiatives are not much popular in Indian Banking Sector. In study conducted by *Suresh Chandra & Bhavana Pandey (2015)*, it was found that if the Indian Banks want to enter the global markets, it is vital that the banks should recognize their working environment and the social responsibilities. The study also highlighted the need for framing the short term and long-term goals in collaboration with their green strategies. Moreover, the management should create awareness among the employees about the needs for having green banking. *Lalon (2015)*, emphasizes that the main reason the public sector as well as private sector banks are not embracing the green banking initiatives is that it needs extensive expenses. The customers preferred to have green banking initiative not because of their social responsibility but also the convenience that the green banking practices added to their life. Most of the customers can reduce their visit to their banks as they are able to get the details of their transaction in their mobile and internet banking. The online banking facility and mobile banking comes under the category of green banking practices.

Purpose of the Study:

- To assess the effectiveness of green banking initiatives from the perspective of account holders
- To identify the initiative taken by banks for sustainable development
- To know the challenges and benefits of green banking

Scope of the study:

Addressing environmental challenges like pollution and climate change requires active participation from financial institutions. Green banking initiatives, though still in their early stages in India, are critical for promoting sustainable practices. This study evaluates the effectiveness of green banking initiatives among medical professionals in Thrissur district, Kerala. The research highlighted the needs for having the socially viable projects to be financed by the banks. It highlights the need for greater awareness and financing of environmentally viable projects to enhance the adoption of green banking practices.

Research Methodology:

The research adopts a descriptive research design to explore the effectiveness of green banking practices from the perspective of account holders. In this study, the focus was to assess the impact of green banking practices as perceived by account holders in Thrissur district, a region known for its rich cultural heritage and commitment to nature preservation. Respondents for the study were selected from a group of doctors working in Thrissur, as the researcher assumed that this group would have a higher level of awareness and knowledge regarding green banking practices.

Data was collected from account holders in both nationalized and private banks operating within the district, resulting in a sample size of 50. Purposive sampling, a method used to select specific respondents from a larger population, was employed to gather information. Due to the challenges posed by the Covid-19 pandemic, direct data collection was difficult. As a result, questionnaires were distributed online to 55 respondents, and 50 completed questionnaires were used for analysis. The collected data were subsequently analysed using various statistical tools.

Table 1: Variables used for the study

Parameter	Customer
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness towards green services • Awareness towards green financing • Sources of information Employees • Awareness towards green banking initiatives of the bank • Promotional measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perception 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perception towards the meaning of green banking • Perception towards the benefit of green banking. • Perception towards the meaning of green banking • Perception towards the benefit of green banking- • Perception towards the challenges of green banking
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tangibility • Reliability • Responsiveness • Assurance • Empathy
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convenience • Time • Cost • Benefit
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time • Cost • Technical problems

5. Result and Analysis

The results of the study and presented in the following section.

Working Hypothesis:

Ho: There is no difference in the proportion of the respondent’s perception about the customer service quality

H1: There is a difference in the proportion of the respondent’s perception about the customer service quality.

Table 2: Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S Test)

	Observed Frequency (Fo)	FO(x) Observed Frequency	CFO(x) Cumulative Observed Frequency	Expected Frequency (FE)	Expected Frequency Proposition FE(x)	Cumulative expected frequency observation CFE(x)	CFO(x)-CFE(x)
Very Happy	3	0.06	0.06	10	0.2	0.2	-0.14
Happy	28	0.56	0.62	10	0.2	0.4	0.22
Neutral	13	0.26	0.88	10	0.2	0.6	0.28
Less Happy	2	0.04	0.92	10	0.2	0.8	0.12
Not at all Happy	4	0.08	1	10	0.2	1	0
	50	1		50	100%		

Interpretation:

The results from the K-S test revealed a D-value of 0.28, which is greater than the critical value of 0.19. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant difference in respondents' perceptions of customer service quality. This suggests that green banking initiatives do not negatively affect the quality of customer service.

Findings of the study:

- **Bank Visits and Services:** Respondents primarily visit banks for deposit-related services and to seek investment advice from bank managers. Most respondents use internet and mobile banking for transactions but are unaware that these services are part of green banking practices.
- **Cost Reduction:** Many customers prefer online transactions due to the reduction in transaction costs. In the past, interbank transactions and NEFT/IMPS were subject to fees, but most banks now offer these services without charge. This cost-saving factor contributes to the preference for online banking.
- **Social Responsibility:** Some respondents expressed willingness to support green banking initiatives as part of their social responsibility. They noted that green banking practices, such as paperless transactions, align with sustainable development goals. Due to their busy schedules, they feel they can contribute indirectly through these practices.

- **ATM and Mobile Banking Usage:** Respondents indicated that they rarely request receipts for ATM transactions or point-of-sale purchases. The convenience of ATMs, especially for after-hours transactions, was highlighted as an important service. However, some respondents reported delays in mobile banking transactions, particularly during peak hours (11:00 AM to 3:00 PM).
- **Awareness and Promotion:** Respondents noted that banks are not actively conducting awareness campaigns about green banking. Many respondents learned about green banking through friends or social media platforms like Facebook and WhatsApp. It was suggested that advertisements, especially SMS notifications, could be an effective way to raise awareness about green banking.
- **Green Banking Adoption:** Respondents highlighted the increased use of online payment platforms like Gpay, PhonePe, and Paytm. Some respondents reported that certain banks, such as SBI, HDFC, and ICICI, offer rewards for online transactions, which further incentivize the use of digital banking services.
- **Green Banking Incentives:** Green banking practices extend beyond digital banking to include environmentally conscious initiatives like supporting solar panel installations or promoting rainwater harvesting. Some respondents mentioned that bank managers had inquired about these initiatives when discussing home loans.
- **Environmental Benefits:** Respondents acknowledged the advantages of green banking, including reduced transportation costs and a smaller carbon footprint. Online receipts were noted for their convenience in record-keeping, as they are easier to store and manage than paper receipts.

Suggestions

- The bank should enhance its customer service to ensure that customers can have their queries addressed promptly, particularly as many individuals conduct online transactions at various times throughout the day. It would be beneficial to offer customer service support 24/7, allowing customers to receive assistance whenever needed.
- The banks should offer additional rewards to incentivize customers to complete transactions using ATM cards and other digital platforms.
- Many respondents indicated a lack of awareness regarding green banking practices. It is recommended that banks increase their efforts in advertising and raising awareness about these practices, particularly through online channels. Promotional campaigns should emphasize the benefits of adopting green banking services such as ATM services, mobile banking, and internet banking.
- Banks should actively promote eco-friendly initiatives and projects. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) should monitor and evaluate the performance of green banking

initiatives across banks and rank them accordingly. Furthermore, RBI should recognize and reward banks that are making significant efforts to promote green banking practices.

Scope for Further Research:

Green banking has gained significant attention as it not only promotes environmental sustainability but also enhances operational efficiency. Ongoing research continues to explore its application across industries. Green banking encourages entrepreneurs and industrialists to invest in projects that prioritize resource efficiency and sustainability. It reduces paperwork by relying on online transactions, streamlining processes. However, despite its growing importance, banks face high operational costs related to digitalization and the need for specialized skills to train customers. The study, conducted among professionals in Thrissur district, highlighted that professionals have fewer banking transactions compared to businesspeople, whose transaction modes differ. Further research could explore the perceptions and expectations of industrialists regarding green practices. Additionally, few nationalized and private banks in India are actively engaged in in-house environmental management and sustainable financing, suggesting a need for more studies on their contributions to environmentally viable projects.

Conclusion:

In developing countries like India, economic progress is closely tied to ecological considerations. While banks' financial support can drive wealth creation, it may also contribute to environmental degradation. Green banking has emerged as a crucial concept, driven by advancements in technology and changes in customer behaviour. With support from the state, central government, and the Reserve Bank of India, green banking practices can significantly reduce pollution and promote sustainable growth. This study, based on data from doctors in Thrissur district, highlights that green banking in India remains largely in the awareness stage, with limited implementation. Customers view these practices as an extension of digital banking services, emphasizing the need for broader adoption. The RBI must encourage nationalized banks to prioritize green initiatives and make "going green" their core motto.

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